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Manufacturing technology problems

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MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RISK MANAGEMENT MECHANISM IN MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract:

Objective. Improvement of risk management mechanisms in production enterprises is of particular importance. Because risks are characterized by different levels of danger depending on the type. This article provides detailed information about risks in the management of production enterprises and their classification into types and levels when taking into account the amount of damage.

Methods. The research methods were statistical, comparative analysis, induction and deduction methods.

Results. The scale of business in our country is increasing, which leads to meeting consumer demand, increasing the scale of national production, and increasing the share of production and services in the GDP, but there are always different levels of support for businessmen. Participants face financial or other types of losses as a result of the mysterious factors. It is especially important to improve the risk factor management mechanisms affecting the stability of production enterprises. In this article, a scientific proposal and practical recommendations have been developed to prevent risks affecting production enterprises and to improve their management.

Conclusion. Sometimes the risks have a high level, and their level of danger can increase the amount of the company's losses, sometimes there are insignificant risks, which almost do not affect the net profit, and can lead to a violation of the management mechanism. From this point of view, it is desirable to improve the mechanisms of their management, regardless of the level of risks.

Keywords: production, risk, risk levels, light industry.

Introduction. One of the main types of production is industrial production. The essence of industrial production consists of two types, which are divided into heavy and light industries.

Industry is the largest and leading branch of material production. The majority of labor tools (tools), labor goods and consumer goods are created in it; all types

of machines and mechanisms, structural elements of buildings and structures are produced; mining of underground resources is carried out; mineral, vegetable and animal raw materials are processed, consumer goods are made, etc. [1]

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis, touched on this

and noted that "... in the reporting year, the balance was achieved in the economic and social spheres of our country, and high speeds were ensured due to modernization and diversification, which is a clear confirmation of this. . That is, ... 161 large industrial facilities were put into operation in our country in a short period of time. They say that this will allow us to produce an additional 1.5 trillion soums worth of products next year [2].

Methods. Statistical analysis methods, monographic observation, induction and deduction, abstract thinking, economic-mathematical modeling, expert and rating evaluation methods were widely used in the research process.

Literature analysis. Industrial risk should be understood as a risk arising from any type of activity related to the production of products, their sale, commodity-monetary and financial operations, marketing, commercial, socio-economic and scientific-technical projects [3].

A. Grigoryans stated in his scientific research that "Risk in industrial production is defined as a generalized characteristic of the situation, a decision-making process in conditions of uncertainty, if some reason does not allow to make an optimal decision to achieve the goal, then it creates a risk" [4].

When talking about the historical development of industrial production and its main results, the scientist of our country A. Artikov, it should be noted that the development of "Home industry" in the territory of modern Uzbekistan dates back to 12-15 thousand years ago - in the Mesolithic period. started During this period, very simple work tools and items were made. During the New Stone Age (Neolithic, the beginning of the 5th millennium BC), shipbuilding and textiles appeared. At the end of the Neolithic period, metal weapons began to be made. It is known from archaeological finds that the people living in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan knew how to make copper weapons at the end of the 3rd millennium BC [5].

Sh.D.Saidboyev, K.Sirojiddinov, one of our scientists, noted that "threats (risks) faced by industrial enterprises mean the possibility of occurrence of factors that cause damage to enterprises or adversely affect the smooth running of production processes." [6].

Results and discussion. As a result of the liberalization of the economy, expansion of production and wide opportunities for business activities, the industrial economy is recording growth from year to year (Table 1).

Table 1

Structure of the manufacturing industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan (as a percentage)⁴

No	Name	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
1	Production of textile products	13,9	13,1	11,8	12,0	13,7
2	Clothing production	5,1	4,1	3,6	3,4	3,5
3	Manufacture of other finished goods	0,9	0,7	0,6	0,6	0,6

The table shows that the production volume of textile products in the industry increased by 1.7% in 2021 compared to 2020, but decreased by 0.2% compared to 2017, and the volume of clothing production decreased by 0.1% compared

to 2020. The indicator decreased by 1.6% compared to 2017. The production of other finished goods recorded a similar indicator in the last three years, but it also decreased by 0.3% compared to 2017.

⁴ Author's development based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The production of industrial production includes many sectors, among the sectors, the sector with a high share with its growth figures from year to year is mainly textile production.

"On urgent measures to support the textile and knitwear industry" to support and further develop the textile and knitwear industry today Decree No. PF-5989 dated May 5, 2020 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted [7]. The decree stipulates the implementation of the following measures:

- rapid solution of transportation and logistics issues of raw materials, materials, finished products, as well as production employees of textile and sewing-knitting industry enterprises;

- development and implementation of measures to reduce the cost of manufactured textile and sewing-knitting

products and increase their competitiveness;

- search for new promising foreign markets, stimulate the export of local textiles and sewing and knitting products;

- tasks such as the development of clothing designs and collections and their introduction to network enterprises are defined.

As a result of the implementation of this decree, it will contribute to the development of textile enterprises and improve the mechanisms of its state support and management.

By establishing an effective management system in industrial enterprises, it will be possible to reduce the effects of risk in production. The essence of risks in industrial production is different and they affect different criteria of activity (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The main risks in industrial production⁵

It can be seen from the picture that the risk of supply includes situations related to the delivery of raw materials. Operational risks are associated with various accidents, destruction and losses that may occur in production. Financial risks are related to the effect of interest rates of loans or investments on production profits, while sales risk is directly related to fluctuations in the economy and market balance. Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida risklarni boshqarish mexanizmlarining o'ziga hos uslubiyoti mavjuddir. One of the most

important of these is, of course, risk assessment. There are many approaches to the theoretical foundations of risk assessment, including economic analysis, mathematical modeling, SWOT analysis, sociological survey, evaluation matrix, and others.

The main purpose of the risk assessment matrix is based on the results of risk analysis and assessment, so the assessment matrix is an important component of management (Table 2).

⁵ Муаллиф ишланмаси

Table 2

Risk assessment matrix in manufacturing enterprises⁶

		Risk assessment matrix			
1	Big losses	II	II	III	III
2	Losses	II	II	III	III
2.1	Heavy	II	II	III	III
2.2	Light	II	II	III	III
2.3	It doesn't matter	II	II	III	III

As can be seen from the table, risks are divided into small types for the production enterprise: large losses and the probability of causing losses are being promoted. Also, the loss factor itself consists of three components: heavy, light and insignificant. Big losses can occur on the basis of technological, household and financial effects. Losses are divided into 3 types: heavy, light, insignificant. Heavy losses are risks arising mainly from financial losses. Small losses create supply and market risks. Insignificant losses occur due to temporary interruptions of medical resources, delays in supply, and other minor problems.

Conclusions and suggestions. If we make a conclusion based on the risk assessment matrix in production enterprises, it shows the need to develop effective mechanisms of risk management and put it into practice. The word "mechanism" is used more often in works related to technique and technology, and this term is also used in modern economy and research works of scientists. Especially in the field of management, the term "mechanism" is widely used in the development of many economic and management models, and the term mechanism is used to make several types of factors appear as a single whole.

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⁶ Муаллиф ишланмаси

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